

BIOCHAR AS PARTIAL SUBSTITUTE FOR PEAT WORKS AS PLANT GROWTH PROMOTER, NUTRIENT BOOSTER AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY ENHANCER

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Abstract

The use of peat in traditional agricultural systems and nursery enterprises is an environmental preoccupation. Since the high CO₂ and greenhouse gas (GHG) emission due to peat excavation and transport contributes considerably to climate change and global warming it is key to find alternative material which can substitute this limited resource. One of this represents biochar. As a potential highly recalcitrant and aromatic “humic substance” (HS) it was shown to promote sustainable agriculture, contributing to the concept of circular economy, leveraging biomass waste and boosting nutrient recovery and use efficiency. In this work we partially replaced peat with different amounts of biochar obtained from vineyard pruning as plant growing substrates whereas implementing N (Nitrogen) fertirrigation. We studied the effect on the growth, different content of N forms and other nutrient dynamics impact of lettuce plants grown under greenhouse and semi-hydroponics conditions. Substrate mixtures contained 30% of vermiculite and 70% of different biochar:peat treatments as follows: 0:70 (B0), 15:55 (B15), 30:40 (B30), 50:20 (B50), and 70:0 (B70). Higher biochar treatments increased pH and electrical conductivity of the substrate, negatively affecting plant growth and germination. The substitution of 30% peat by biochar (B30) delayed seed germination but improved plant growth and N use efficiency without showing stress symptoms. This is related with a higher nitrate (NO₃⁻) retention capacity in the substrate, leading to higher allocation and flux of N to the plant shoot and a better performance of N metabolic enzymes (NR, GS, GOGAT, GDH). The treatment B30 also increased the water holding capacity of the substrate, which may enhance soil moisture characteristics and pore size distribution, maximizing water availability to plants.

Our study demonstrates that the use of biochar can reduce the consumption of peat and excessive N fertilizers, while showing how nutrients differ, especially N, under the different Biochar/Peat “competition” scenarios for nutrient sorption and plant nutrient content. This ultimately promotes a more sustainable agriculture with positive impact on both the plant growth and the environment.

Keywords: Biochar, Lettuce, Nitrate assimilation, Nitrogen, Peat

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